

USE OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC NEMATODES AGAINST PESTS OF CUCUMBER PLANTS GROWN IN GREENHOUSE CONDITIONS**Denov entrepreneurship and pedagogy institute support PhD student****Norboyeva Umida Erkin qizi**

Abstract: Insects for pathogen was nematodes entomopathogenic called nematodes. Entomopathogen nematodes quarantine and another Dangerous pest insects ideal biological for struggle qualities have This in the article entomopathogenic nematodes greenhouse conditions cultivated cucumber plant pests against apply about word was conducted.

Key words : entomopathogen nematodes , greenhouse , cucumber plant , biological fight , nematode , insecticides , pest insect , entomopathogen .

Nematoda - means eye to us pest insect will come . Of course, that's right pest nematodes the number very a lot They are village household products in cultivation big harm delivers They are of the plant land bottom from part to top to the part harms. Theirs damage because of yield is up to 50-60% lost there have been years . Today village household crops biological to protect according to from entomophages trichogramma , bracon and from golden eyes efficient we are using . Today again one biological to protect type in our country wide current to do we are on our way.

The world according to useful nematodes biological struggle purposes trichogram and bacillus thuringiensis from next 3 - eng a lot used bioagent is considered Insecticides danger because of organic in farming alternative as application can.

Useful nematodes into 100 categories from 200 belonging more than pest to insects against efficient to apply can In particular, the chest worm , fruit flies (cherry fly), moths (east fruit eater), root worms (simkurt) and others.

Useful nematodes omnivorous microorganisms , its size very small and to the eye not visible , nematodes only light or electron in the microscope enough level magnification with to see can Harmful to insects against struggle as useful nematodes plants , animals and to people harmful impact does not show and this ecological clean solution is considered them wide open from the fields from , to most modern greenhouse also use in facilities can Entomopathogen nematodes pests no of doing proven method as is becoming popular. Entomopathogen nematodes quarantine and another Dangerous pest insects ideal biological for struggle qualities have The world according to useful nematodes biological struggle purposes trichogram and

bacillus thuringiensis from next the third the most a lot used bioagent is considered Insecticides danger because of organic in farming alternative as application can.

hectares in India in 2017 1,200 tons in the field work issued and used.

in Germany fruity 95% entomopathogenic in gardens from nematodes is used . Today our scientists by Uzbekistan _ in the area from nematodes to use efficient to the road to put according to research take is going Useful nematodes into 100 categories from 200 belonging more than pest to insects against , for example , kosak worm , fruit flies (cherry fly), moths (east fruit eater), root to worms (simkurt) . against efficient apply can.

In nematodes of crops each how soil pests against in the struggle of a person main ally is considered Useful nematodes only in the soil lives and they are their own nutrition for, of life a lot part pest of an insect in the body conducts and with him is fed Almost all to live in places occurs, they bacteria with symbiosis developed and own in turn insects kills . Nematodes each different kind of of insects out of a thousand more than types load to do able, from the egg except of development all stages impact does.

Nematodes 48 hours inside pest the insect dead does.

Useful nematodes much durable Belong to in temperature if stored (4°C), one for how many months vitality save standing can.

Useful nematodes harmful in insects to them relatively natural or acquired resistance (adaptation) to the body doesn't come

Ecological in terms of safe soil, air , natural entomophagous , warm-blooded animals and a person to the organism never how negative effect does not show .

High to productivity have become one useful from nematodes within 10 days face thousands generation harvest to be can.

Useful nematodes year during increase and apply can.

Useful nematodes biolaboratory conditions increase technique

Biolaboratory conditions increase process:

Necessary equipment :

Useful of nematodes motherhood material

Wax moth larvae

Plastic dishes

1 hectare field for 1000 wax moths larva plastic to the bowl put 30-40 ml on it motherhood material is useful nematode suspension is poured .

Darki in the room or on top of it to the part black cloth closed for 10 days at a temperature of 15-28°C is left. From this after _ dish on the wall watery, slimy, yellowish spots it seems

In the field to apply process:

In the morning or evening cool and the sun straight away __ not coming down at the time, useful nematodes 1000 infected wax moths larva 5 liters in a bucket to water for 20 minutes let's leave it. From this then, in the bucket 1 hectare of liquid field for 300-600 liters to water mix. Desired water sprinkle from the equipment using in the field we use

20,000 hectares in India in 2017 1200 tons in the area work issued and used .

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Entomopathogen Nematodes about

Nematode of the drug quality indicator - 1 g watery in suspension nematodes 5 million of the number. from grain less not to be

One hectares to the field worker solution consumption - in irrigation water with together 200-400 l/ ha when distributed , from irrigation before 1000-1500 l/ ha when distributed

In nematodes spending plant type depending on - one bush from 125 thousand to 2 million per plant. up to 5-10 billion pieces per hectare nematode

Nematodes optimal development for temperature 20-28, some 25-30°C in strains

Nematodes to apply optimal requirements for:

- Humidity above 75% to be _
- The sun upright rays not falling (early in the morning or evening cool);
- Air temperature should be 15-25 °C;
- Worker solution in preparation water temperature should be 15-20 °C, from 30°C high temperature in the water nematodes dead be begins;
- Worker in solution of water index 4-8, hardness 5 need.

In nematodes effect what he did how to know possible - nematode with damaged insects the color o' changes, if Heterorhabditis with if damaged pink-red to color, Steinernema with if damaged yellowish-brown color will change.

Summary by doing in other words , in the future useful nematodes to apply our province scale wide promote to do as a result village household from crops phytosanitary clean , organic and good quality product get opportunity more expands .

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